

Ignition Timing Sensitivity of Methanol Spark-Ignition Engines: Insights from In-Cylinder Combustion with Coated Pistons

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Abstract

Enhancing engine efficiency while minimizing heat transfer losses remains a major challenge for the automotive industry. In this study, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was employed to analyze the combustion and flow characteristics of a four-stroke variable compression ratio (VCR) spark ignition engine (2.5 kW brake power) fueled with a methanol-gasoline blend (M20: 20% methanol, 80% gasoline by volume). To reduce heat losses, the piston crown, cylinder liner, and cylinder head were coated with a 300 μm thick copper layer. The engine was evaluated under three ignition timings (26°, 27°, and 28° bTDC). The CFD results showed that copper coating combined with methanol blending significantly enhanced combustion behavior. The in-cylinder pressure increased by 1.74%, 5.2%, and 4.85% at 26°, 27°, and 28° bTDC, respectively. A maximum flame temperature of 2418 K was recorded at 28° bTDC, while combustion velocity and turbulence kinetic energy also improved with methanol addition. Overall, the findings suggest that copper-coated combustion chambers, in conjunction with optimized ignition phasing, can substantially improve efficiency and combustion stability in methanol-fueled SI engines.

Keywords: SI engine, copper coating, Methanol, Ignition timings, Combustion characteristics

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to concerns about pollution, a lack of accessibility, increasing fuel scarcity, and the quick depletion of fossil fuels, researchers have been working hard lately to discover a variety of unique renewable energy sources. In addition to its benefits for the environment and lower carbon content, alcohol was the most popular alternative fuel to conventional petrol. The fluid flow characteristic is one of the most significant aspects influencing engine performance. Thus, several researchers have worked on the internal combustion engine [1] suggested that the combination of air and fuel benefits more from air turbulence. The thermodynamic principle model was utilized to estimate the variations in gas pressure inside the cylinder. The model is also assessed for its ability to predict the angle at which sparks ignite and the length of the burn [2]. With the assistance of a FORTRAN program, [3] performed wave action conducting fluid flow through simulation in the ICE's combustion chamber and obtained data on the velocity and pressure distribution at different boundary conditions within the cold flow in a twin cylinder engine. [4] employed a fluent two-dimensional transient simulation analysis to get temperature, velocity, and pressure when using a crank angle. [5] utilized numerical computation and ANSYS to analyze the fluid characteristics in GDI engines and depict the flow pressure throughout power stroke and compression.

By using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), [6] analyzed an inlet manifold and demonstrated how the cylinder's internal Swirl Ratio (SR) varied depending on the crank angle for various manifolds. The research conducted by [7] focused on how different engine layouts affect GDI engine performance. According to CFD research conducted at different engine speeds, a compression ratio of 10:1 at an engine speed of 4000 rev/min. Finally, a low heat release rate at a fuel injection pressure of 200 bar was identified. To investigate and calculate the flow parameters at constant speed and crank angle for standard octane fuel operation [8] worked on the numerical modeling of the engine operating conditions. He solved the governing equations using the simulation software ANSYS V15.0/ICE CODE. Piston thermal behavior was studied by [9] using the finite element approaches. They applied piston thermal boundary conditions were results very close to the experimental results. It was determined and observed NO had a good agreement throughout the equivalence value of 0.8-1.1. The evaluation of flame speed [10] has been adjusted at an equivalent level (0.9) which represents the highest NO.

The piston conversion of heat was studied by [11] utilizing a resistant-capacitor model. Some places in the piston are represented as capacitors in their model. The paths it takes to connect them are considered difficulties. The engine's other components receive the heat from the piston ring, skirt, and pin on the other side of the piston. For estimating combustion chamber wall temperatures developed a computer program for transient heat conduction in components (HCC) in two dimensions (axisymmetric). Their findings were validated for simpler test problems using a finite element approach [12].

Furthermore, their model was tested on real-world problems and reported that they are in close agreement with the research results. The research was conducted on the numerical model of a two-stroke engine. The numerical model, convergence, and flux conservation qualities are demonstrated on the engine performance and the predictions are shown at a high-performance 125cc engine and a medium-performance 100cc engine [13]. The performance was improved by an existing quasi-dimensional model to accurately estimate the surface temperature field in burned and unburned gases. To simulate the engine cycle, a k- ϵ turbulence model was used [14]. For a two-stroke SI engine, [15] developed a heat release approach. The simulation analysis has been utilized to determine the suddenly released heat and density consumed by the basic and catalytic engines.

The high combustion ignition retards were examined by [16] concentrating on the effect of spark retard and pressure distribution through the surface. The temperature and mass of the gas inside the cylinder were estimated under various spark timing situations. [17] conducted research on Thermal barrier coatings (TBC) can increase engine thermal efficiency, enhance combustion, and reduce emissions. Ceramics also have the advantage of being more resistant to wear than standard materials. Reduced temperature rejection within the engine chamber by thermally insulated materials leads to more and the amount of energy conveyed by exhaust gases. The design algorithms for distinct innovative levels like parametric condition and configuration have been defined by [18]. They can be used in the design of computer-aided engines (CAD). The design parameters, process simulation hierarchy, engine simulation, and future development requirements were specified. [19] created a three-dimensional finite element analysis (FEA). It describes the thermo-mechanical behavior of a direct-injection diesel engine. The findings would serve as a starting point for developing a worldwide elastic hydrodynamic model, in addition to being a valuable tool for piston design. The heat transmission to an engine piston crown has been examined by [20]. The combustion boundary condition is calculated using three different ways. A KIVA-3V and NASTRAN code interface has been developed.

Thermal studies on diesel engine piston heads made of aluminium-silicon alloy and steel have been investigated by [21]. The surface temperature of a coated piston engine head has low thermal conductivity and materials for AlSi alloy and steel are improved by around 48% and 35% respectively. The optimization of an I.C engine has been developed by [22] In-cylinder pressure is the engine performance that's being looked at, while CO and NO levels are the emissions that need to be reduced. The SOI timing was changed between 120° to 140° at a spark ignition time of 19° to evaluate the influence of injection timing. compared experimental data with CFD analysis of a two-stroke engine. The experiment has been carried out with the assistance of a motor, in which a rotating engine is formed with the help of a motor and without the use of a fire. After validation, there seem to be relative inaccuracies between experimental and modeling methods that should be evaluated [23]. The multi-zone model was investigated, which is gaining popularity as a fast and effective computational model for HCCI combustion simulations [24]. A comparative study was conducted in this paper to determine the impact of several sub-models on the multi-zone model's prediction capabilities. The combustion analysis (CFD) code is utilized to model complex combustion phenomena in compression ignition (CI) engines in the current work. The results of the modeling were compared to the outcomes of the experimental inquiry. The cylinder pressure and net heat release consequences were discussed [25]. The research's findings illustrate internal combustion engine simulation can also benefit from computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modeling.

The rate of heat transfer in the combustion chamber using various fluids and a fixed manifold. When increasing velocity, CFD research shows that pressure decreases and velocities and heat transfer rates are improved [26]. The experimental research on internal combustion engines and used CFD to develop the inlet manifold flow behavior. To increase the transfer of heat, it is suggested that the flow behavior be modified with the ideal engine speed. An unsteady flow was created for successful combustion [27].

A. Objective of the study

The investigation aims to develop a combustion simulation analysis to determine the fluid flow characteristics of spark-ignition engines. The dynamic mesh technology was used to design the combustion chamber and to visualize the flow there using the ICE code with an engine speed of 3000 r.p.m. CFD program is used to do a computational combustion and emissions analysis of a gasoline engine. (Ansys-ICEM/CFD/Fluent*TM). The three-dimensional model of the combustion chamber was drawn using ANSYS workbench and by developing ANSYS FLUENT CFD, the combustion chamber's dynamic meshing has been completed. The standard combustion and emission models are used in the analysis. The contours of velocity, pressure, and temperature will be examined when compared to various spark ignition timings.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Methodology

At present a lot of pressure to improve internal combustion engine manufacture and design. Engine design at present must be light in weight, strong, flexible and powerful. To meet these needs, innovative engine designs will be necessary. Because internal combustion engines (IC engines) are made up of complicated fluid dynamic interactions between air-fuel flow, fuel injection, moving parts, and combustion, the ability to reliably predict the performance of numerous engine designs is extremely important and necessary. The flow phenomena can be quantitatively analyzed and visualized on a 3D geometry using CFD data, which offers a great deal of understanding of the intricate interactions that take place inside the engine.

B. Coating Material

The materials used for coating are chosen based on their properties. An exceptional material is created using its mechanical, physical, and chemical properties. For the coating of a combustion chamber and piston many coating materials are available. Zirconia, nickel-chromium, aluminum oxide, molybdenum, titanium, and copper coatings are among the coatings that are most appropriate for IC engines [28]. Copper contains high electrical conductivity. So, this material is widely used in engine applications. Plasma spraying coats were made on the piston head and inside surface area of the cylinder head of a single-cylinder four-stroke, VCR spark ignition engine. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 depicts the plasma-coated piston's schematic arrangement. The physical characteristics of copper, a good thermal and electrical conductor, and a corrosion-resistant ductile catalyst are as follows. Table 1. represents the properties of copper [29].

Fig. 1 Conventional piston

Fig. 2 Copper-coated piston crown and cylinder head

Table 1. Properties of Copper

S.No	Property	value
1	Allowable Temperature (°c)	1083
2	Strength (MPa)	221
3	Density (gm/cc)	8.94
4	Thermal conductivity (W/m-k)	400
5	Specific heat (J/kg-k)	386
6	Coefficient of thermal expansion (10-6/k)	17
7	Young's modulus (Gpa)	115

C. Methanol and gasoline blend properties

Experiments are conducted on several engine configurations, such as conventional engines (CE) and copper-coated engines (CCE) using various test fuels such as 80% pure gasoline and 20% methanol (M20) blended fuels. Table II. lists the attributes of test fuels.

Table II. Properties of Test Fuels

S.No	Property	Gasoline	Methanol (ASTM)
1	Chemical formula	$mC_n H_{2n}$	$CH_3 OH$
2	Molecular weight	112	32.042
3	Composition (by weight -%,)		
	Carbon	84	37.48
	Hydrogen	16	12.5
	Oxygen	Nil	49.9
4	Specific gravity at 15.5oC	0.7 to 0.75	0.796
5	Boiling point oC	30	65
6	Latent heat of vaporization (Kcal/kg)	70-100	264
7	Vapour pressure at 58°C	0.8	0.32
8	Lower calorific value (Kcal/kg)	10500	4700
9	Mixing heating value(Kcal/kg)	714	734
10	Self-ignition temperature °C	300-450	478
11	Cetane number	8.14	3
12	Octane numbers		
	(a) Research	91(Regular)	114
	(b) Motor	82(Regular)	94

III. COMBUSTION CHAMBER MODELING

The process of simulating geometry was carried out by selecting the single-cylinder four-stroke water-cooled petrol engine with a brake power of 2.5 KW at a constant speed of 3000 rpm was employed in this study as shown in Fig. 1. An 80 kW METCO plasma spray gun was used to apply coating material of Nickel Cobalt Chromium (Ni-Co-Cr) with an average thickness of roughly 100 μm . Copper was 89.5 %, aluminum was 9.5%, and iron was 1.0 % were coated with a thickness of 300 μm over the bond agent. After 50 hours of continuous operation, the coating thickness has high bond strength and will not wear away. Additional details regarding the engine specifications are listed in Table III.

Fig. 3 Schematic illustration of the experimental setup

Table III. Specifications of the test engine

Make Greaves Limited		
S.No	Parameter	Description
1	Bore	70mm
2	Stroke	66.7mm
3	Rated output	2.5KW
4	Max Speed	3000 rpm
5	Spark timing	25obTDC
6	Compression ratio	3:1 to 9:1
7	Specific fuel consumption	475 gm/ kW h
8	Lubricating oil	SAE-40

ANSYS FLUENT R 19.0 (Academic) software is utilized to solve the governing equations numerically using the finite volume method with proper boundary conditions. The geometry is modeled in a pre-processor using ANSYS workbench R19.0 - Design modeler in this study ANSYS. On the piston top, the bore was 70 mm. Fuel injection will take place at 25o in bTDC, according to the experimental test rig. With the help of Fig. 4 we can figure out where the valves and spark plugs are located. Similarly, when constructing the geometry, the clearance height was calculated using the same spark ignition timing. The cylinder's air pressure and temperature are maintained at atmospheric values. In the ANSYS workbench, the resulting geometry was meshed. As shown in Fig. 5 the structured mesh is made up of 16, 00,237 hexagonal components. Ansys-ICEM/CFD/Fluent*TM software is used to provide the boundary requirements for the geometry. In the development of the combustion chamber model diameter, clearance volume height, and moving layer height are necessary.

Because of its improved mesh generation and user-friendliness, the finite volume-based CFD technique is utilized for geometric modeling, pre-processing, and post-processing analysis of internal combustion engines. The improvement of combustion parameters and reduction of emission characteristics of the spark-ignition engine were numerically investigated by using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) for the copper-coated engine (CCE) with methanol (M20) blends in the current study. The governing fluid equations were solved using the CFD code. The geometrical realm is partitioned into small grid volumes (i.e. hexagonal components mesh). In the combustion chamber, the k- ϵ model is utilized to simulate turbulence.

Fig. 4 Locating of valves and Spark plug on the Cylinder head

Fig. 5 Computational mesh combustion chamber

A. Turbulence Modeling and Governing equations

Combustion analysis generates heat, work, and product species. In computational combustion analysis, heat is calculated from the temperature and velocity; work is calculated from pressure and density; and the species are calculated from concentrations and velocities. The governing equations of these properties are derived from fundamental thermodynamic, hydrodynamic, and chemistry principles. According to [30] compressible equations for the conservation of mass, Momentum, and Energy equations are governed by the dynamics of fluid flow inside the cylinder.

Conservation of mass:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho u) = 0$$

Conservation of momentum:

$$\frac{\rho Du}{Dt} = \frac{\partial(-\rho + \tau_{yx})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z} + S_{Mx}$$

Conservation of energy:

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \text{div} (hV) \right] = - \frac{Dp}{Dt} + \text{div}(k \text{grad} T) + \phi$$

Conservation of Species:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_m}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_j \rho_m}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\rho D \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial x_j} \right) + S_m$$

Fig. 6 CFD flow chart for IC engines

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A CFD analysis was carried out at various ignition timings of methanol methanol-blended copper-coated engine (CCE). The combustion and emission parameters obtained for alcohol fuel blends were compared concerning copper-coated engines and the characteristic contours and curves were drawn.

A. Combustion characteristics at a thickness of 300 (µm) with spark ignition timing

1. Pressure contours:

The pressure is greatest near the core and decreases towards the periphery. According to theory, negative flame fronts arise when flame fronts impact the cylinder walls, leading to the production of localized high-pressure zones near the cylinder walls, as seen in Fig. 7. As indicated in the graph, there are high-pressure zones around the cylinder walls. Also, as the spark ignition timing is increased, the combustion pressure increases.

(a) Pressure for 26o bTDC

(b) Pressure for 27o bTDC

(c) Pressure for 28o bTDC

The effect of 300 μm thickness of copper-coated engine (CCE) with methanol (M20) fuel at various spark ignition timings on peak pressure as shown in Fig. .7. Due to the various heating values of the combined fuels, M20 copper-coated has a maximum pressure of 16.9 bar. With a higher compression ratio and wide-openthrottle, peak pressure rises. Because the pressure and temperature of the mixture during sparking are higher at higher compression ratios, and heat generated during combustion further enhances of pressure and temperature. When the ignition time is changed from 27°bTDC to 28°bTDC, the pressure increases marginally. CCE M20 had a peak pressure of 15.24 bar at 26°bTDC, 16.08 bar at 27°bTDC, and 16.9 bar at 28°bTDC.

Fig. 7 Pressure for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (C) 28°bTDC

2. Temperature contours:

The temperature contour graphs at full load for methanol blends with copper-coated engines are given in Fig.8. At greater compression ratios, the peak temperature for sparking is higher and heat generated during combustion boosts the temperature and pressure even more. At the same time apparent flame speed rises at shortening the period of combustion. The effect of a

copper-coated engine (CCE) with methanol (M20) blend at various spark ignition timings on peak temperature is shown in Fig.8 [a, b,c]. As the spark ignition moves from 26°bTDC to 28°bTDC, the temperature progressively rises. CCE M20 reached a peak temperature of 2386 K at 26°bTDC, 2403 K at 27°bTDC, and 2418 K at 28°bTDC, respectively.

(a) Temperature for 26o bTDC

(b) Temperature for 27o bTDC

(c) Temperature for 28o bTDC

Fig. 8 Temperature for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (C) 28°bTDC

3. Velocity contours:

In the velocity contour plots, the base of the combustion chamber can be seen. The combustion velocity is higher along the engine cylinder walls as shown in Fig. 9. The flame speed is unaffected by the compression ratio for this reason combustion time decreases even if the compression ratio rises the maximum gas temperature increases, resulting in a quicker apparent flame speed. These factors have a big influence on engine performance. With the valve timing that allows for a backflow into the intake manifold, the highest velocity was achieved. Because fast speed creates a high vacuum at the intake port and hence a large airflow rate inside the cylinder, it leads to great efficiency. The differences in velocity with spark ignition time are shown in Fig. 9. For 9.077 m/s, 9.716 m/s, and 11.04 m/s, the velocity progressively increases.

(a) Velocity for 26o bTDC

(b) Velocity for 27o bTDC

(c) Velocity for 28o bTDC

Fig. 9 Velocity for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (C) 28°bTDC

4. Turbulent kinetic energy contours:

combustion in internal engines needs air-fuel mixture and in-cylinder turbulent flow. High turbulence can affect knocking and turbulence in the engine produces kinetic energy also identified as turbulent kinetic energy. Fig. 10 illustrates that the global trend of the contours is the reduction in the TKE values observed as a result of the increase in the ignition timing.

Fig. 10 Turbulent kinetic energy for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (C) 28°bTDC

It is noticed that turbulent kinetic energy decreases with 26°bTDC to 28°bTDC for methanol methanol-blended copper coated engine. The turbulent kinetic energy values are found as 8.92 m²/s², 8.42 m²/s² and 7.356 m²/s². In Fig.10 [a, b,c] the average turbulent kinetic energy was reduced by 5.6% and 12.6% with 27°bTDC, and 28°bTDC respectively.

B. Emissions characteristics at a thickness of 300 (µm) with spark ignition timing

1 Mass fraction of Soot Contours:

Fig. 11 Shows the soot mass fraction of ~~spark~~ engine with a methanol blend. Soot emissions were produced at the center of the spray and then moved to the outskirts of the clearance near the cylinder head. Fig.11.(a,b,c) shows the average soot level at 27° bTDC was reduced by 36.06% as compared to the 26° bTDC and 28° bTDC. The lower C/H ratio of methanol compared to gasoline fuel together with the presence of higher oxygen content which does not affect the environment during the combustion is the main reason for reducing soot formation.

(a) Mass fraction of Soot for 26o bTDC

(b) Mass fraction of Soot for 27o bTDC

(c) Mass fraction of Soot for 28o bTDC

Fig. 11 Mass fraction of Soot for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (C) 28°bTDC

2. Mass fraction of NO Contours:

Fig. 12 Shows the NO contours in mass fraction of copper coated engine with methanol blend various spark ignition timing. This is the result of reduced ignition delay in the cylinder of the engine. Due to the delay in starting the engine, sufficient fuel is accumulated in the combustion earlier for ignition, which in turn leads to complete combustion. Fig. 12 Shows the oxide of nitrogen values for copper-coated methanol with blend 26° bTDC, 27° bTDC and 28° bTDC such as 2.285×10^{-3} , 1.947×10^{-3} , and 3.014×10^{-3} respectively.

(a) Mass fraction of NO for 26o bTDC

(b) Mass fraction of NO for 27o bTDC

(c) Mass fraction of NO for 28o bTDC

Fig. 12 Mass fraction of NO for various ignition Timings (a) 26°bTDC (b) 27°bTDC and (c) 28°bTDC

CONCLUSIONS

The current paper shows the improvement of CFD modeling for the turbulence and combustion simulation in spark-ignited copper-coated engines (CCE) was presented.

- The combustion pressure increased by 1.74%, 5.2 %, and 4.85% as a result of copper copper-coated engine with a thickness of 300 μm with spark ignition timing of 26o bTDC, 27o bTDC, and 28o bTDC.
- The combustion flame temperatures were noticed at 2418 K at 28o bTDC for is high compared to the 300 μm. if the copper coating thickness on the piston head is raised, the coating bond on the piston surface is destroyed when the pressure and temperatures are increased rapidly.
- The combustion velocity and turbulence kinetic energy were increased on methanol blending at 300 μm. With methanol blended at 300 μm, both the mass fraction of soot and the mass fraction of NO were observed.

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